

Expert 1	Benefits	Limitations	Remarks
Applicability	<p>I am convinced, I see these as very realistically applicable. If the question is whether it is acceptable for an end user, and technically doable, having set the stage for the designer with a framework to describe, my answer would be yes. I am basically thinking of the mock-up that you showed me. I think this is all perfectly understandable. It is easily controllable by the end user. If what runs behind that was properly set in terms of framework, in terms of initial framework implemented by the designer, then it works. I think it is a sound and solid framework, in my opinion.</p> <p>Also, this element that you introduced, where depending on the choice, you are streamlining the process, in a way that it is, I think that the key word here is intuitive. So based on the mock-up, that is definitely intuitive. And it avoids mistakes on the side of the consumer. It avoids choosing configurations that are not manufacturable later on, and it maintains the process in a very safe, visually understandable manner. So, I think it is a sound approach.</p>		

<p>Feasibility (technical)</p>	<p>I think it is technically feasible, up to the point of having the algorithms that is controlling the entire process.</p>	<p>My understanding and impression are that this is doable. But so far no one has tried doing it. So, there may be reasons for that.</p>	<p>I think the delicate steps here would be to connect that all to your manufacturing process. That is why I asked you the question earlier about how far you are aware in generating a program for the knitting machines, because eventually, when all these is done, you need on one end a set of data that can run a knitting machine and on the other hand, a set of data that run a 3d printing machine to print it out. So, these are crucial elements.</p>
<p>Potential (business)</p>	<p>Potential is enormous in my opinion here in general perspective. Because I think it is the perfect companion the kind of shoe construction that you selected, knitted upper with 3D printed sole.</p> <p>Streamlining the process by automating knitting programming and 3d printing is very promising.</p> <p>The design flexibility framework, and the user involvement in the design, gives an additional boost to the to the basic, already busy winning idea of having a simple shoe that you need. And they are basically assembled by gluing it out on an apparatus. So, I think the potential is high.</p>	<p>With all the caveats that we must keep in mind in relation to how functional, how good, or resistant is now for 3d printing them. We know that we are not fully there yet in relation to doing 3D printed soles that are really usable in real daily life, but technologies are moving fast in that direction.</p>	<p>If all the “residual problems” will be solved, then these kinds of shoes are winning, they are based on a winning design, because they are simple to make, easy to assemble, it is just a few steps. So, they are compatible with many different scenarios or localized production, compact manufacturing plants and so on and so forth. So that is the potential that I see there.</p>
<p>User experience / satisfaction</p>	<p>You can make it more or less attractive in graphical UI by giving 3D rendering of your shoe. Because I think one element that should be somehow implemented there is also engaging the consumer in something that he finds fun doing. So that is part of how you design your user interface. Also, it is like a game. It is basically gaming with your shoe design; you change something</p>	<p>There is one element that should be carefully considered is that at final, ending of this user satisfaction process is when he gets the shoes, and the shoes are doing exactly what they promised they would have done in your configuration process, or are they fitting properly? Are they</p>	<p>Adding functional properties of the outsole could be very beneficial and have potential for the users.</p>

	<p>you see the effect. It is like targeting a certain outcome and being happy when you achieve what you had in mind. And you see the result in rendering, that is all fine.</p>	<p>comfortable? Are they functionally as they wanted? Are they graphically as I told them when I designed the shoe? So that is part of the process robustness and the profitability of the process.</p>	
<p>In comparison to existing applications</p>	<p>I am not aware of anything similar that goes close to what you are doing. What you do in a classical customization exercise is you are somehow giving, given the size of shoe that you want to have, the choice of a few selected parameters. There is no interconnection with a functional effect that you achieve when you change your design. I think the winning point here is that you combine fit, aesthetics, and function in a way that I saw nowhere else. So, I think it's unique.</p>		

Expert 2	Benefits	Limitations	Remarks
Applicability		<p>Knitting on the Kniterate is limited on gauge. If you want to make it broader that you would actually be able to knit it on a Stoll or Shima machine. Then you would be also able to change gauges, which is also interesting for this. You can basically have a final gauge. So let's say you have a 14 gauge machine, but they have bigger needle hooks. So they take more yards, and then you could either use it as a potting gauge, or you can use every second needle and then having a second gauge gene basically. If you skip one, you need thicker yarn to fill up the space. When you need bigger needle hooks to take that.</p>	<p>Thinking about is knitted shoes, most of the time have very different zones in there. So you can, for example, also use a yarn that's called heated yarn. So you have a yarn, and whenever you steam it, it melts away invests into the other yarns. That is great, if you want, for example, a heat counter in there or some support. So that is something I could think of nice for the functionality. Do I need more support here or there? Then it would be maybe nice to add.</p> <p>One more thing that you could maybe add is changing the stitch length in the knitting. Yes. So you could actually make looser or stronger knits. Maybe that's also something that you can use for the elasticity option you have. So whenever you need a very sturdy one, you could just tighten up the stitch length.</p>
Feasibility (technical)		<p>I'm wondering about the why you chose these knit structures for shoes, because most prefer to use double bed knits. Single jersey isn't really giving any Yeah, I have cardigan actually stretches more than that. It would hold the foot in place. Yeah. And</p>	<p>Flat bed knitting is not the most cost efficient that you can do. Then circular knitting would be more cost efficient. But then at the same time, you can do the customization pattern in the flat knitting</p>

		<p>also for the graphical pattern; that cannot easily be applied to these structures. So the best would be actually use jacquard.</p>	<p>machines and can not do in circular knitting. It also depends on the structure you use. So actually, I guess you would have to adjust the costs based on the structure and the material you use. Because some patterns just take longer to knit. Normally, knitting is paid by the minute so you pay a knitting machine by the minute; for example, one of our machines cost 42 cents per minute that it runs. Most of the knitted uppers are constructed as a three color jacquard and most of the knitting machines have three systems so they can let these three yarn carriers in one go and that makes it very cost efficient. But whenever we go to something like a four color jacquard, then it would take double the time because it needs these three yarn carriers in one go, then it has to move the carriage back and then takes the forth yarn carrier so that takes about double the time.</p>
<p>Potential (business)</p>	<p>Where I see actually the greatest potential is that it would also affect the fit very much. And not only the graphics. Because I think some people really struggle to find a perfect fit for their application if they want to have running shoes that perfectly fit. If you could adjust that to your own needs, I think that is something that would be really great. I mean the graphic side is a nice add-on. I think everybody enjoys. But the real potential I really see is in this bit.</p>		<p>How the upper and sole put together is the challenge in mass customization, because then that's actually manual work you have to do. I'm thinking of the loop shoe from adidas, made entirely of TPU. So the knitted upper and the sole are binded together just by heating up. it's also enough to have the bottom part of the last, like just the insole, to stick them together.</p>

	<p>I'm thinking about if you have orthopedic insoles, you could only adjust the sole. So you don't need the insole, you have it in one go with the sole.</p>		
<p>User experience / satisfaction</p>	<p>Positive if you have a great fitting shoe afterwards. I think it also depends on how long it would take to ship them out. Because everyone is so used to getting things the next day. I think that is one challenge in user experience. But I think as long as you can really measure to the needs that you have, then it is worth the wait.</p>		
<p>In comparison to existing applications</p>	<p>If you already know what functionalities you need, you don't need to make that many decisions. Maybe users want to customize the shoe for fitting or functionality. Creating or designing sides are more difficult for users.</p>		<p>I am just thinking of one example, Unmade. There's a challenge because it didn't work out in the end. I mean, they produce quite well, but now they're doing something else. And I think it was just not there yet, for this. They were producing knitwear sweaters based on jacquard. And then it had some predefined settings, and then you could change the colors, change the graphics on there, and then get you one of the kind of products. I think what they also had a challenge with returns, because then you having a product that is individualized, but yeah, you need to take it back. So you can not sell it to anyone else. I think that there's also change a bit in society and how you buy things and how you also cherish things that are individualized. So I think this was a bit too early for everyone to pick it up.</p>

			<p>In terms of graphics, maybe better once you have very restricted things that you can adjust. E.g. change colors on graphics that already exist. Or only change the graphic in a certain way and not invent a whole new graphic.</p> <p>Basically, by having two options where like the people truly want to get creative can get creative with guidelines.</p> <p>You could also think of artist editions, where someone else design it for you.</p>
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Expert 3	Benefits	Limitations	Remarks
Applicability		I was thinking that you don't mention orthopedic applications, which I think are probably the most personalized shoes that you can find at the moment.	
Feasibility (technical)	I think technically it is possible with knitting. it's so depending on the type of machine that you're using, what exactly is and is not possible. And I'm just so happy that I don't have to write the algorithm to communicate all that. I think that's mostly what I'm thinking about, how do you make the algorithm so that it recognizes all of the rules in knitting? At first there's a few rules in knitting things that you can and cannot do with a specific machine, perhaps as well. But then there's the unwritten rules of things that just don't work as (that) well. I think there's a lot of expertise, that you need to be able to miss things.	So technically, I can definitely see that it would be complicated. That doesn't mean that it's impossible. You know, you need technicians either way, when you start doing these kind of things, as long as you can find the right people. Yeah, I think it's possible.	The algorithm with co-dependencies between material, yarn count and stitch pattern, but also maybe stitch size, I think it's good. I mean, it makes life even more complicated, of course, for whoever is doing the algorithm. But you know, you can you can knit with the exact same yarn and the same stitch, but change the stitch size and have like a completely different result. And there are some complicated co-dependencies that I did not see reflected as much yet and I don't know if it's necessary, but I think that is something that you would need a technician for usually.

Potential (business)

In terms of business potential, maybe also bigger potential, I think it's kind of linked to the mission that Kniterate has, where you democratize fashion again and give it back to the people so to speak. And you can make your own designs. I do think that, of course, you're thinking about a very, like, fully automated situation, but where Kniterate is if you make a customized item.

I think it's mostly about knowing who your market is, probably the most complicated then find a market that it fits. Because even if you keep all the ultimate automations, they're still going to be hand labor. And you can never compete with fast fashion. You know, personalized shoes just cannot be made in the same speed as the same shoe.

I think because of research, you have a bit more options, because as soon as you're a business, then you actually have so many things to balance. Of course, it becomes hard to actually get to the point.

A similar example is with compression hosiery. There are both standard sizes and also fitted ones. These are also mass personalized and the costs are not necessarily much more expensive. About making customized items like on our machine, we wanted to offer that for a not tailor price. But of course, because of the amount of manual labor that is still required to produce anything on a Kniterate, you are still quite close to the tailor price, especially compared to fast fashion. But if you compare it to other sustainable fashion brands, then you're more in the same space. You're talking about a fully automated setup at some point, which would of course be different. So if you would have that, then you would definitely be able, I think, to serve a healthy, that's like a big business out of that. Whereas, as long as there's manual labor needed, you always have a limitation in terms of how much you can produce. If you would go to business case from this, I would do lots of simplifications, I would make it a lot more simpler to make it a bit more cost efficient, or maybe more simple. And also depends on the user profile as well. But of course, like in research, it should be also a bit of forward looking. So not today, but also it's more thinking about the future.

<p>User experience / satisfaction</p>	<p>So I think that there's probably quite a lot of people who would be interested in this, because, you know, fashion doesn't fit. I know I would be very psyched about it. Because I have one foot, it's like full size bigger than the other one. It's just annoying at times. So if your service/products is able to provide two different sizes for the same person, that's really nice, because I know that plenty of people have this course.</p>	<p>If you can get your shoes, in this case, choose any products in a reasonable amount of time, and reasonable being way too fast, because people can get their ready made shoes the next day. Most people don't want to wait that long. I know from some sustainable fashion companies, for example. You can pre order things. And then you might wait for a few months, maybe one or two. But I do think that there's a limit on how long people are willing to wait. (in terms of knitted fabric properties) I think people won't necessarily understand what they are changing. And that's actually quite important. And people often don't know what is what. People don't know the difference between woven and knitted, let alone different methods structures.</p>	<p>I think the trick is in the user experience, like the user interface as well, to make it easy to use. That's definitely what we are noticing in developing our software. How to make sure that you can involve every level of user. Yes, it is tricky. Because at some point, you will encounter someone who doesn't know what a JPEG is. (about different knit patterns) There is a visual attraction to certain stitches opposed to other stiches. So I think it's good to have a way that you can communicate how they behave differently. So maybe in a preview, you always have like a little image and a little description, or you have a shoe made of that fabric, and then that it's like a gif that moves so that someone can see how the fabric moves. Inform them as good as possible of the materiality because of course, you're talking about a translation between digital and material as well, which is always quite hard. You could use video, or moving image quite well to communicate certain things that you would be able to test out in a store, but you wouldn't be able to see that from scen.</p>
<p>In comparison to existing applications</p>	<p>I'm just thinking that I have made my own vans and converse countless amounts of times and I never ordered them. But then you have the limitations of their fabrics etc. You were talking about being able to upload your own images or to draw. So it can really be fully of your own hand, which is really cool. So there's a</p>		<p>As I mentioned, I thought of the the compression hosiery, which is, of course, way more medical and like a needed thing. And I'm thinking that there is a big difference in the type of people that would be attracted to your product, whether</p>

higher customization/personalization level in there. So I would definitely say that it's beneficial that you have more freedom compared to vans or converse, probably Nike and Adidas have the same.

people needed or wanted. Because if you really have a big shoe size difference between your feet, if you have two sizes different or something, or if you have your graduation or wedding or whatever coming up, and you just want some really, really awesome shoes, and it's definitely a want and then there's of course 100 things in between.

Expert 4	Benefits	Limitations	Remarks
Applicability	<p>It is applicable on the condition that you should take account the functional constraints. They are the hardest, and they are actually the core. So static and dynamic. And so, if you, for example, have the user input, and in your case, maybe you should say that I just do shape, and texture, and runs(?), and also moisture and heat, which are nice. But if you, for example, would extend to personalize shoes, I think the weight of the user is also something to consider the weight distribution and stepping. But your matrix and your algorithm are general enough to cope with these additional things. So, you should take that into account. Not made in the full technical details. But as the purpose is to show that it is applicable for shoe design, this should also take into account. Because we go into the technical details of the knitting and the insole. So, I would say this example is confined to the geometry.</p>	<p>You are very limited to the methods of production of different parts. You also chose something very complex mechanical and dynamical and heat loads. The personalization aspect there is the point where your weight is in contact with the ground and where your movement take place. Now you are using 3D prints and knitting to test how users can interact and limit the design space to their needs. But the methods are maybe not too restrictive to have good methods to also for generalizing things. So, it's not tailored to a shoe. So maybe your conclusions will be very general then. You also need specific knowledge for you on production, and by exploring the user flow in in this co-creation. Also restricted to some exciting new technology, but still may be too restrictive to see or reveal what is the pipeline of, of that design in the co-creation process. There are very exciting elements in it, like knitting and the 3d printing and scanning. But as you cannot make a shoe a functional shoe, it is maybe not tackling the whole process.</p>	<p>There should be many more constraints but as tech advances and becomes available you can add rows or columns to the dependency table. It is fun and exciting what possibilities there are. But the shoe is more of a functional thing. Yeah. Yeah. You. In young, this is the surface of the shoe. And yeah, definitely, definitely. It is not in the in surface the efficacy of fit, and connection with the ground through your insoles. So, it is nice, but it is only very partial. Exploring that you are limited and maybe you should consider the limitations of your technology used in the case study towards the generalization of the use of flow of the cocreation flow, you want to pinpoint. I am a bit on the validity of the link between your dependency matrix to tune the design space to the solution space. I think that is nice, and your algorithms are sound. But then you use methods that are not valid for shoe design and for shoe fabrication. I'm not saying that you should abandon these but be very aware of those limitations related to your general</p>

			<p>framework. On one side, it is very abstract, which is nice, on the other hand, it is very tangible, which is also nice. But the tangible parts and aim of the general framework to validate it, they are not in 100% match. And that is okay. But be aware of that. And so, in your presentation, you go into details of the parameters, which is also nice. But it is not the entirely validated much the case to your general framework. Maybe you should think of tricks to decouple that a bit. Because the argument, it is just designed just the case. Think of another purpose or think of sharpening the purpose of your case. Otherwise, it is a very abstract framework. But I think it can work to build algorithms for personalization, it will definitely work and think of your personalized shoe as a showcase rather than a shoe design case(?).</p> <p>Maybe you should throughout the course of the argument of designing a shoe, that you just say I leave the functional parts behind, I am not focusing that. The applicability of the presentation to shoe design. That is the question to formulate feedback.</p>
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<p>Feasibility (technical)</p>	<p>I think the feasibility is definitely there. And also, the demands because we used to come from a time where the shoe was personalized, or fully personalized and then we got away from it, now we can return to that. But I think the role of the expertise, or the expert system is important. And users just want a good shoe. And then Okay, maybe they know on certain aspects. I am without shoes now, I like it. Because my foot is too warm all the time and too much moisture. So, I know that then probably. That is something people know. But I think you should not give them too much, not asking too much input on the personalization. So, user aspect is also there on the feasibility.</p>	<p>Your processes and the techniques and the technology you have used are more and maybe most on the cosmetic level. So, what you can do is fit and you're shaped to some extent and color. But, this is not a shoe. It is just the outer layer. Yeah, yeah. The End layer of a shoe. But to dive into that, Or maybe it is not yet feasible.</p>	
<p>Potential (business)</p>	<p>I do see potential in the constraints, dependencies, and the rows and the columns of the matrix in that matrix tend to tune it to an algorithm.</p>		
<p>User experience / satisfaction</p>	<p>That is whether the personalized product as a good user experience and enhanced satisfaction. I think psychological and social factors should be taken into account. So it can be investigated with these methods. And on the co-creation process, I think it's nice. People are used to sliders and how they change and direct visualizations. So yes, it could help on the inputs of their parameters themselves. Not entirely sure. But you should facilitate it. both stress. Choice stress, we say in Dutch gives us stress. I think there can be a huge difference in cultures and definitely in gender. Male have different attitudes to shoes and also for female it's different. So, you should differentiate in gender groups. The Gay gender is a spectrum and how you</p>		<p>Did you consider the psychological and social factors here?</p>

	<p>used to choose is also spectrum. But that is something to consider, if you want to elevate the impact of personalization.</p>		
<p>In comparison to existing applications</p>	<p>It is a niche somehow. You express yourself through shoes. It is also something very fundamental. It is a means to move and when you are on the move, it draws attention. It also says a bit on the group you are belonging to. So, I am not sure if people do want to personalize their shoes. Some youngsters, people that feel a bit outside or, but I think everybody wants to have a personalized shoe.</p>		<p>it is just also a gut feeling that I expressed. So, it's something I thought of, but of course, feel free to disagree and take your own approach to it. But, the main point is that your shoe is a difficult thing and it's a good topic. And then you have on the other hand, the enablers, the knitting and 3D printing and the scanning, which is also very nice. And on the one hand, you have the demonstrator, and you have the methodology to link that design space to the solution space, which is very nice. And then you have the shoe as a case, and the technology as an enabler. And there are some gaps, but it is okay. But I'm looking forward to the work.</p>

Expert 5	Benefits	Limitations	Remarks
Applicability	<p>I think it is quite clear the use case, it is quite similar to twikit technology. Of course, the whole story is you design the design templates, where all the restrictions and the possibilities of changing that personalizing it, and they get the interface where the user interacts, or the end customer interacts with the configurator and defines all the all the aspects. Of course, due to the limitations and restrictions, you can only do certain things, if you select the need for parameter A x, then it will also interact parameter B, like the amount of possibilities for parameter B will be less because you picked x in here. So, I definitely understand the whole logic about it. I really like the fact that you are thinking further than just esthetical personalization that you're really thinking about functional personalization, because that's quite new I believe, definitely in the footwear industry. The interaction between those parameters like heat resistance, then it will impact the knitting pattern that will impact the openness and those kind of things. It is very interesting that it is like an interlocking system. So yeah, that is my first feedback. Very, very impressive.</p> <p>I totally agree that it can be applicable in the footwear industry. Why? You see it in the last couple of years or last decades, the people are really looking for personalized footwear. If you're looking at running</p>		

	<p>shoes, or other sports shoes, or just walking shoes, like they really want to know everything of the shoe. And you currently have applications popping up at Adidas and other. For example it's really like applications that communicate the whole your health, of course, but also the way you walk. And I think people really want to have that data to see how that shoe is performing. That's during usage. But before when designing the shoe, people, definitely in the shoe industry, they want to have it personalized. And the more freedom you give them, I think they're really becoming a co-creator, and they're becoming their own designer. And I think the footwear industry is ready to implement this type of application. So, I think the moment is really here, I think it will all depend on how fast they can change their production process to this kind of applications. Because it's quite new and innovative, of course, but like I mentioned, I think having your list of parameters, they can change, and you can completely customize in terms of heat resistance and those kinds of things. I think that's, that's something that's going to come in the shoe wear industry, it's just a matter of time. But I think it will be there.</p>		
<p>Feasibility (technical)</p>	<p>I think it will still take quite some time to really implement this. Like today you can already customize your shoe based on pressure scans or 3d/2d scans. Pressure scans are already being used, 3d scans is a little bit more challenging for shoe wear for insoles. It is okay, it is already being used, but shoe wear it's more challenging. And I think the limitations is really, the fact that a shoe exists out of different parts, like you mentioned, you get the upper part you get the sole, you get the outer sole, you get the midsole, you get</p>		

sometimes an insole as well, in a shoe is a very complex product and is assembly in different parts. And, of course, your application, it only exists on two parts, you get the upper part and then the sole itself. But I think it will be more complex, I think more layers of material needs to be added. I think that is the big limitation of making it possible. Because the assembly is just quite extensive for a shoe, at least today. But again, visibility, like especially looking at 3d printing, that is already being used at New Balance, at Adidas. They're looking at 3d printing as a digital technology to create a design that is very distinguished from issues that are out there today. And they are also looking at incorporating 2d scans and 3d scans to the shoe based on the user inputs. But also, the knitting, like you mentioned it is similar to 3d printing, it's just a different technology. But it is also a digital technology, it uses inputs, customer or user inputs. And I think knitting is something that people are also looking into. We have some partners also in the field of shoe wear that are looking into adding esthetical patterns to those kinds of fabrics. But really changing it based on heat ability and those kinds of things, that's really an added value and very innovative and I have not seen that before. So, I think feasibility, I think the challenge will be to make production suitable and to bring down the complexity of shoes to really make this possible. And to have it as a scalable solution, I think that is the most challenging thing. The shoe wear they're still focused on mass production, the shoes are more or less the same. Okay, you can change some colors but more or less the shoe is the same and I think here you really customize it to the individual customer. And I

	<p>think that is a big challenge to change your production system to more customized approach.</p>		
<p>Potential (business)</p>	<p>I think that's really what Twikit represents. Custom designs until today, or until a few years ago, it was very labor intensive. If somebody wants to have a custom design, there's really a designer that needs to create a production, design briefing and there you need to use a CAD program or some something else to create that individual design. And by using that algorithm and by using or by automating that whole design flow, and giving the customer the possibility to design their own shoes, you give them the responsibility to become their own designer. You can really create a scalable solution for unique one-of-the-kind of products and that design automation has huge potential. It is something that, of course, Twikit is doing for years now, you see it in shoe wear industry, but also in other industries, that this is the new way of creating products and selling products, and it will only increase in the upcoming years. That will also give designers of footwear brands more freedom, and more time to really create a design concept with 1000 different possibilities with just a few limitations. And that you are able to create a million different variations of just one single shoe. And I think that's the biggest potential of this kind of application.</p>		

User experience /
satisfaction

I totally agree with the way you presented it like having that user flow of going through configurators step by step guiding them through that process of designing your own shoe or own product is the way to go. It can be online through a web shop, it can be in a dealership. I think the only challenge will be to not make it too complex for the customer. You are now working with sliders, those different parameters. But for me, with less knowledge about shoes, for example, what is heat ability? And what is openness of a pattern and like what do I have to take into account? I think it is really important that the customer is guided and supported during that design process. If you add those functional parameters, like I just mentioned, I think that is the biggest challenge. But I think the user experience is very interesting. But also, if I am looking at this application, I think customers also want to see the difference between the fabrics, they want to feel it, they want to see it, touch it. I think that is an opportunity for this application that somewhere in the user flow. People can really interact with the material. Maybe it is not necessary today, I also buy shoes online, but I think different types of fabrics, people would like to see and feel how it looks like. I think that can really that bring the user experience to a higher level. And there is one aspect that I have not raised. I am not sure if you already think a part about it is the sustainability part. What if all these shoes are custom made for the specific user? What if they throw it away? Is there something you can recycle or reuse? Or what if something gets broken? Let's say the upper part is broken, do they have to reorder? Or do they have to go through the whole flow again? Or is this saved

	<p>somewhere on a database? I think those are some aspects you should think about as well are recycle aspects and what if something gets broken? How do they reorder? I think that is important as well to take into account.</p>		
<p>In comparison to existing applications</p>	<p>I think maybe it's interesting for you as well to look it up, it's a company in the United States, it's called voxel eight. And they have a kind of digital technology, where they can print, it's also like a type of 3d printer, silicon-based material on fabrics. So, when I get somewhere I get here, samples my component. So they can print silicon on fabric and that could be for functional reasons, because it helps to create stiffer parts on the fabric, just by pouring a very thin layer of silicon on that area. But it can also be for aesthetic reasons. Because on top of that silicon, you can also print ink. I think they currently work already for a lot of shoe brands just for research and developments. But it's a very interesting technology that you could definitely explore as well. So, it's actually a layer on top of fabric. So, it can be a layer on top of the knitted fabric. I think that that's one specific application that I currently have in mind that I remember the next day in footwear industry. Most and most, and I already shared that earlier. Of course, like the new balance and the Adidas 3d printed insole, 3d printed soles. They're specifically focusing on combining it with 3d scan data or 2d data or pressure data. I think that is a very added value of having a shoe and also the sole completely shaped around your foot. Because I do not think that is in the in your application, the idea or because it is</p>	<p>It was a very clear presentation. Like I mentioned, I really like the idea. There are some challenges, but there are a lot of opportunities as well. And I think it is really going to be the future of shoe wear, that you can change all the different aspects of the shoe. In terms of esthetical personalization, also function personalization. So I definitely like it, though my knowledge about digital knitting is a little bit less. But I think it is very interesting type of technology. And it is also digital so that it really fits in that manufacturing 4.0 scenario. So it is a very interesting project. And I am glad that I would have heard it.</p>	<p>it's for me hard to compare to existing applications. Since I am not aware of any application today that is similar to yours. I know, from New Balance and like, a data source. That's your type of application that's new to me. So it's really hard to compare it. But that I think it's an added value of your project, that it's quite new and unknown, let's say, especially looking at those different functionalities and parameters even change.</p>

	mostly focused on the top part, of course, yes, but there is also the sizing, that's fixed sizing, right?		
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